

Deliverable D-JRP21-WP6.10

Workpackage 6

Responsible partners: BfR, SVA,
IZSLER, APHA

Contributing partners: AGES/VMU,
ISS, RKI, IZSAM, PIWET, NVI, NDRVMI,
VRI, WBVR/UU, VFL/EMU

GENERAL INFORMATION

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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

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Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media:
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BIOPIGEE

Workshop 2 completed

Participating institutes (in the workshop organisation)

BfR, SVA, APHA, IZSLER

Further contributing institutes

ISS, VFL/EMU, RKI, WBVR/UU, PIWET, AGES/VMU, VRI, NDRVMI, IZSAM, NVI

Background and objective

The workshop was originally planned to take place as an one-day event in conjunction to a relevant conference in order to disseminate preliminary results from the BIOPIGEE project and to adjust data collection in running studies according to input from stakeholders. Due to the covid 19 pandemic, the implementation of the event was delayed and changed to an online format. The expert panel from BIOPIGEE Task 5.4 (that added estimations on measure effectiveness earlier) was invited, representing a part of relevant stakeholders. The objective of this online workshop was to share and discuss first findings on the effectiveness of biosecurity measures studied in the BIOPIGEE project with the panel members and to exchange ideas about how to disseminate findings to stakeholders (e.g. farmers and veterinarians).

BIOPIGEE project

The zoonotic pathogens Salmonella and hepatitis E virus can cause acute and chronic diseases in humans. The most common transmission route is assumed to be foodborn from pigs. The aim of the project BIOPIGEE "biosecurity practices for pig farming across Europe" of the One Health European Joint Programme is to identify effective and cost-efficient biosecurity measures for the reduction of these pathogens in the pig production chain in order to prevent human infections. To achieve this, different literature reviews, field studies, experiments and transmission/cost modelling are carried out. Finally, it is the aim to inform stakeholders like farmers, veterinarians, authorities and the pig industry about the findings on best biosecurity practice.

Invitation

The invitation, as follows below, was sent to the expert panel from BIOPIGEE Task 5.4: 47 professionals like veterinarian practitioners, advisors, consultants, industrial experts, governmental staff, researchers and scientists on November 11th 2021. A reminder was sent, including the finalised workshop programme, on December 2nd 2021. The BIOPIGEE project group was informed about the upcoming workshop on September 28th 2021 and repeatedly reminded, incl. the final programme on December 3rd 2021; the whole group were invited. A link to the web tool (MS Teams) where the

meeting was hosted, organised by SVA, was sent to the participants several days in advance to the workshop.

Invitation to a workshop

November 2021

Dear professional,

You were previously invited by the BIOPIGEE project ('Biosecurity practices for pig farming across Europe') to a survey on the effectiveness of biosecurity in relation to *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus (HEV) in pig production. The survey has now been closed and preliminary results have been analysed. We would now like to welcome you to attend an online workshop on 14 December 2021 from 10 am – 2 pm CET where preliminary results will be disseminated and discussed, and we can update you on the other areas of progress within this project. This invitation is to give you the chance to save the date. A detailed agenda for the workshop including a link to the online forum will be distributed in advance to the workshop. You will have the chance to only attend parts of the workshop depending on interest and availability.

To register, please use this link:

<https://forms.office.com/r/S3xz4rfiCF>

In case you have any questions, you are very welcome to contact the coordinator of the project at biopigee-coord@bfr.bund.de via mail or via telephone +49 30 18412 24307 (BfR).

We kindly ask you not to forward this invitation but if you feel that we have missed to include someone who should be invited, please let us know.

Kind regards,

Programme

The programme (to find below) included four sessions with 14 short presentations from different BIOPIEE work packages and tasks as well as discussion rounds with the expert panel and the project group at the end of each session. The first session was about why the project is working on the pathogenes Salmonella and and hepatits E virus, on what biosecurity means and what we have learned so far from the literature on the effectiveness of biosecurity measures regarding the control of these pathogens in the swine production chain. The second session was about findings from field and experimental studies on the effectiveness of biosecurity measures. In the third session, studies on transmission of pathogenes on farm and along the food chain were presented and discussed. The fourth and last session focused on the expert opion about measures' effectiveness and an overall discussion between the project group and the panel.

Workshop programme

One Health EJP

Grant Agreement number 773830

Date / Time	14 th December 2021 / 10am – 2pm CET
Venue	Online Workshop, organised by SVA, BfR, APHA, IZSLER
Meeting	OHEJP BIOPIGEE Workshop
Room	Hosted by SVA in MS Teams

10:00-14:00 **BIOPIGEE Online Workshop 14th December 2021**

Biosecurity measures to control *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus (HEV) along the pig production chain in Europe

Chair: BfR/Elke Burow - Chat: NDRVMI/Gergana Krumova-Vulcheva - Notes: APHA/Elisabeth Waller

1. Session - Theoretical introduction

10:00-10:15	Why a project on these pathogens? (<i>Salmonella</i> , Ivan Rychlik, VRI; HEV, Marina Meester and Tijs Tobias, UU)
10:15-10:25	Definition of biosecurity/ biosecurity measure (Nikolaus Huber, VetMedUni)
10:25-10:30	Content of biosecurity categories in BIOPIGEE (Elke Burow, BfR)
10:30-10:50	Literature reviews (Primary production, Slaughterhouse, Giuseppe Aprea, IZSAM/ Arvo Viltrop, EMU)
10:50-11:00	Discussion
11:00-11:10	<i>Short break</i>

Chair: APHA/Richard Smith - Chat: IZSAM/Giuseppe Aprea, Daniela D'Angelantonio - Notes: RKI/Genevieve Sohl

2. Session – Studies in BIOPIGEE on effectiveness of biosecurity measures

11:10-11:25	Implementation of biosecurity measures on farm and <i>Salmonella</i> / HEV occurrence (Hannah Jones, APHA)
11:25-11:35	Effect of individual farm measures (UK/IT) (Enrico Pavoni, IZSLER)
11:35-11:45	Findings on slaughterhouse biosecurity practices - online survey (Tarmo Niine, EMU)

11:45-12:00 **Disinfection and biofilm** (*Salmonella*, Mardjan Arvand, RKI/ **HEV**, Renate Hakze, WUR)

12:00-12:10 **Discussion**

12:10-12:40 *Lunch break*

Chair: APHA/Robin Simons - Chat: VRI/Petra Vasickova - Notes: PIWET/Artur Rzezutka/Jacek Zmudzki

3. Session – Modelling of the effectiveness (costs) of biosecurity measures

12:40-12:50 **Studying transmission of HEV between pens and batches within farms**
(Marina Meester and Tijs Tobias, UU)

12:50-13:10 **Modelling of *Salmonella* and HEV transmission, effectiveness and economics** (Robin Simons, APHA and Stefan Widgren, SVA)

13:10-13:20 **Discussion**

13:20-13:25 *Short break*

Chair: ISS/Ilaria di Bartolo, AGES/Christopher Prigge - Chat: SVA/Beth Young - Notes: VetMedUni/Nikolaus

4. Session – Experts opinion on the effectiveness of biosecurity measures

13:25-13:40 **Expert opinion on biosecurity statements** (Erika Galipo, APHA)

13:40-14:00 **Overall discussion**

- How is best biosecurity practice in European pig production characterised (based on literature, studies, experts)?
- Conflicting opinions and differences with literature?
- How to disseminate results?
- ...

14:00 *End of the Workshop*

Participants

A total of 62 participants from 11 countries attended the workshop (see Table below). Most of the participants were members of the BIOPIGEE project, 11 participants were part of the expert panel, the rest were interested guests additionally invited by the project group and the panel members.

Number of Workshop participants

	AT	BG	CZ	DE	EE	IT	NL	NO	PL	SE	UK	Total
BIOPIGEE	4	1	1	5	2	6	2	1	3	3	7	35
Panel	1			2		2	3			1	2	11
Guests	1		2	2	1	4	1		2		3	16
Total	6	1	3	9	3	12	6	1	5	4	12	62

The workshop

The workshop took place as planned. The first presentations on the pathogens pointed out a need for (well timed) controlling the transmission of these pathogens along the pig production chain. Control by biosecurity practice, in turn, first requires agreement on what is meant by a biosecurity measure. A definition from the project group, including active implementation of specific procedures (simplified here; complete definition is in the publication process) was suggested followed by a lively discussion in the chat and at the end of the session. It was stated that biosecurity measures are taken in the environment of the animal and prevent pathogens from reaching the animal and that veterinary medicine like vaccination would be used when biosecurity measures failed. Several participants agreed on this. Further measures were discussed to clarify assignment to biosecurity. Also BIOPIGEE biosecurity categories and literature findings on effective measures in primary production and at slaughter were presented.

In the second session, studies and first results on the effectiveness of farm and slaughterhouse biosecurity measures were presented and questions on disinfection for biofilm as well as on HEV diagnostics and analysis were clarified. The audience had no hints for the evaluation of the farm and slaughterhouse survey.

The third session presented first findings and experience from observational studies on transmission of HEV between pigs on farms (to find out when pigs in a pen become infected – only fatteners were found positive in this study) and results from modelling transmission of HEV along the food chain. It was asked for the definition of a HEV positive pig and the number of parameters deciding for stabilisation of the model.

The last session focused on the experts' opinion. The experts' assessment of the relevance of biosecurity measures and categories was presented. Experts rated their expertise highest for Salmonella and

indoor housing of pigs. Categories like cleaning and disinfection as well as mixing of pigs were ranked high for both pathogens and production systems. Country or region based differences were suggested to analyse for. In the overall discussion the question on how to disseminate results was focused. It was stated that descriptions of procedures linked to biosecurity measures need to be available in several languages for targeting those that really implement biosecurity measures on farms. The need for translations was agreed on. Illustrations or comics were suggested to be helpful. It was further emphasised that informing people is an essential process for changing behaviour towards a correct application of biosecurity measures. Moreover the information would need to be adjusted for the respective audience. In BIOPIGEE it is planned to produce and disseminate pictures and short slogans for farming schools. More languages could be considered. Consideration was given that people could not yet know technical biosecurity terms in their own language (similar as for animal welfare several years ago), and that education would be of high importance. In contradiction, it was stated that despite existing knowledge of biosecurity measures, they are not applied as people do not get any credit for the implementation, which points to the need for guidelines and policy regulations. The discussion was stopped as it was 2pm and the workshop ended.

Conclusion

The workshop provided an overview of the first results of the project and important discussion points were taken up. Insights from the discussions were gained mainly regarding the definition of biosecurity measures, laboratory diagnostics with respect to biofilm and pathogens, and the stakeholder orientated processing and dissemination of results. More discussion time for deeper and more comprehensive diving into some topics would have been desirable.

Future work

The ideas and conclusions derived from the workshop will be considered and incorporated in the future work in the project tasks and dissemination of results. Another workshop is planned for 2022. More room for discussion, possibly in smaller groups if possible in the frame of the event, is being considered for this.

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